

Best Practices for preprint peer review services in the use of AI

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Executive Summary

This document provides guidance for preprint peer review services on the responsible integration of artificial intelligence (AI) tools, establishing guiding principles and practical steps to support transparency, ethical practice, and research integrity.

Purpose and Background

Life science preprints have increased in adoption since 2013 with a growth of journal-agnostic peer review services since 2017. The use of large language models (LLMs) and other AI tools is rapidly changing research and peer review, raising opportunities for improved efficiency and equity but also risks of fraud, bias, and loss of human judgment. These best practices are designed to encourage responsible use of these tools, without being overly burdensome.

Best Practice Principles

The document sets out five guiding principles:

- **Transparency:** AI involvement in reviews must be openly disclosed to all parties, including details of tool capabilities, limitations, and approved uses.
- **Human Oversight:** Qualified human reviewers must make all final decisions or maintain overview of verifying AI generated outputs; AI tools should support expert assessment.
- **Security and Confidentiality:** All AI tools must protect data privacy, and third-party tools need to meet platform standards.
- **Quality and Integrity:** Leverage AI for pre-screening or automated checks. AI tools used should be validated and any reviewers using AI protected.
- **Ethical and Unbiased Review:** Review services must monitor and mitigate any bias introduced by AI and ensure equitable treatment of all authors.

Implementation Guidelines

- Establish public AI policies detailing acceptable tools and uses, as well as disclosure and auditing procedures.
- Include metadata fields and confirmation checkboxes in review forms to ensure reviewers declare and own their use of AI tools.
- Provide targeted training and guidance for reviewers and staff on responsible AI use and policy compliance.
- Audit AI tools and review outputs regularly for compliance, bias, and misuse.

Policy Template and Enforcement

An appendix provides a sample policy outlining permitted and prohibited uses, disclosure and auditing mechanisms, reporting routes, and procedures for monitoring and enforcement.

Conclusion

Adopting these best practices will help peer review services and potentially traditional journals in ensuring safe, fair, and transparent use of AI in scientific publishing, safeguarding integrity and supporting community trust.

Definitions

<u>Term</u>	<u>Definition</u>
Preprint	A preprint is a scientific manuscript posted to a public repository that has no costs for readers or authors. Some fields may refer to this as a working paper.
Peer Review	The evaluation of scientific, academic, or professional work by others working in the same field with relevant expertise. A peer review is conducted, authored and the judgement is a human activity.
Peer Review Service	A journal-independent service that provides peer review for authors of scientific and academic articles, data, methods and other scholarly outputs and for the wider research community and readers of such outputs. For the purpose of this document, this refers exclusively to human-authored reviews.
Artificial Intelligence (AI)	Computer systems designed to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as learning, problem-solving, decision-making, and understanding human-like speech and images. In the context of this document, AI is used interchangeably with LLM.
Large Language Model (LLM)	A type of artificial intelligence model trained on vast amounts of text data to understand, generate, and process human language

Scope

These best practices are designed for any preprint peer review service, evaluation service or journal organising peer review. Although the guidance focuses on the Life Sciences, it is not exclusive to this field. These particular best practices are not designed for peer reviewers themselves. These best practices and associated guidance may be partially applicable to peer review services that rely exclusively on AI approaches, without human oversight.

Introduction

Since 2013, the adoption of preprints in the life sciences has significantly increased (Fig. 1A). Preprints now represent approximately 11% of the biomedical literature (Fig. 1B). Alongside this innovation and growth, journal agnostic peer review services have emerged. These review services have been growing slowly, though bolstered by the COVID-19 pandemic, with approximately 2-3% of preprints being associated with a non-journal organised peer review. Preprint peer review currently has wide differences in adoption across fields (Fig. 1C).

Other disciplines have adopted preprinting to [varying levels](#). In physics and mathematics, preprinting is a standard practice with journal publication a formality. In contrast, in humanities and social sciences, preprinting is much less established.

Figure 1. The adoption of Life Science preprints have been growing since 2013. (A) Preprints indexed by Europe PMC, (B) the percentage of preprints that are associated with a publication (data from Europe PMC) and (C) Reviews of bioRxiv preprints (data from Sciety, until end 2023).

As of 2025, there are at least 20 active preprint review [services](#), each with a different approach to improving the process of peer review. For example, PREreview focuses on improving equity and training whilst Review Commons is focused on making the review process more efficient for researchers and journals.

A more recent innovation has come in the form of large language models (LLM) and artificial intelligence (AI). This has rapidly disrupted the academic landscape as LLM tools have been readily adopted by researchers for every step of the research process. This has had mixed outcomes for academic publishing where inappropriate use of LLMs has produced highly questionable and outright

fraudulent research papers. On the other hand, for the majority of researchers where English is not their first language, LLMs can help with grammar and writing, potentially reducing bias in the publication process. This use is likely to be relatively widespread and where there are current AI policies, this use is largely accepted. However, disclosure of this particular use could be beneficial as a means of highlighting responsible use and normalising the use of these new kinds of tools. This also helps reviewers and authors in not viewing disclosure of AI use as a negative, but rather a standard process.

This mixed impact extends to peer review, where authors have recently been [discovered](#) to be hiding prompts for AI within manuscripts. Peer reviewers are also known to be utilising AI to write review reports, removing human judgement and assessment. The use of AI also introduces additional biases which can further disadvantage scholars that are already facing inequity. However, AI has also been used to help summarise peer review reports, making them more useful and accessible. There are preprint peer review services, such as Rapid Reviews, utilising AI to help identify potential reviewers, which can improve efficiency in the system. In addition, there are now services that rely entirely on AI tools, with no human judgement. For example, [RegCheck](#) utilises LLMs to automatically compare preregistration plans with scientific publications whereas tools such as [SciScore](#) check the integrity of scientific methods covering several checklists, including MDAR (Material Design Analysis Reporting) and STAR Methods. Figure 2 highlights some of the AI tools currently used in peer review.

Figure 2. A selection of AI and LLM tools currently being used in peer review.

Currently, there are [few](#) clear guidelines or best practices around the use of AI in scientific publishing. This includes in relation to peer review. As preprints enable greater experimentation in publishing, preprint peer review enables experimentation with the peer review process. These best practices are designed to bridge this gap and provide guidance to preprint review services that may be subsequently adopted by traditional journals.

Best practices for preprint review services

The best practices are arranged according to guiding principles, with an overview of the key responsibilities of the preprint review services in relation to each guiding principle. The best practices

are designed under the assumption that AI is being used by the review service or reviewers and attempts to guide responsible and appropriate use as opposed to banning use. However, even if a review service does not use or allow AI use by reviewers, the guiding principles are still relevant.

<u>Guiding principle</u>	<u>Review service responsibilities</u>
Transparency	<p>Clearly communicate AI involvement: Inform authors, reviewers, and readers when AI tools are used in the review process (e.g., for triage, language, assessment)</p> <p>Disclose limitations: Make users aware of the capabilities and limitations of AI tools, including potential biases and the need for human oversight</p> <p>Provide a transparent policy on AI use by the service and peer reviewers. This may include a list of approved AI tools</p> <p>Equip authors with the ability to disclose any use of AI</p>
Humans to Provide Final Oversight	<p>Ensure human oversight: All final judgments on manuscript quality, originality, and scientific validity should be made by qualified human reviewers or tools that have been validated by humans</p> <p>AI tools should not be listed as authors but their use should be transparently disclosed</p> <p>Train reviewers: Provide guidance and training for reviewers on how to use AI tools responsibly, emphasizing that AI is a support tool, not a replacement for expert assessment</p>
Security and Confidentiality	<p>Ensure that all AI tools used by the preprint review service protect user data and maintain confidentiality throughout the review process</p> <p>Audit third-party AI tools for compliance with the services privacy and security standards</p>

Quality Assurance and Integrity	<p>Leverage AI for pre-screening: Use AI to identify potential issues such as plagiarism, image manipulation, or missing documentation, but always verify findings with human reviewers or direct users towards evidence of verification for the AI tools</p> <p>Support reviewer efficiency: Allow AI to assist in organizing comments, summarizing manuscripts, or spotting redundancies, but require reviewers to finalize and personalize feedback</p> <p>Support responsible AI use: If reviewers have responsibly used AI then protect them from authors who may use this to discredit the review. For reviewers who repeatedly utilise AI irresponsibly consider sanctions or banning them from reviewing</p>
Ethical and Unbiased Review	<p>Mitigate bias: Monitor and correct for any biases introduced by AI tools in manuscript triage or review assignment</p> <p>Promote inclusivity: Ensure that AI-assisted review processes do not disadvantage authors from underrepresented groups or institutions</p>

Guidelines on implementing the best practices

To help implement the best practices, this section contains guidelines and suggestions for preprint review services.

Develop a public AI policy

One of the most immediate steps a preprint review service can take is to implement a transparent, public, policy in relation to AI. This policy is useful even if the service does not allow AI use as this sets clear expectations to users.

There are a number of preprint review services with policies focussed on AI including [ResearchHub](#) and [PREreview](#). These are helpful references for other services in developing their own policies. Indeed, if the review service is utilising AI this should be communicated in such a policy. This extends to which tools are used, how they are used and how the service ensures that bias is mitigated. For

example, some review services utilise AI tools to identify potential reviewers. This should be communicated, via a policy, along with how the service is ensuring that the reviewer pool is not biased by the AI tools. Ideally, the service would also audit its own use of AI and transparently communicate any issues.

An AI policy should also be directed at those writing the reviews and could include a list of acceptable AI tools (which may have been audited by the review service, or sourced from a third party). The policy may also include a list of accepted use cases for those AI tools, such as in improving grammar. The policy should reinforce the other elements of the best practices that relate to users, such as humans maintaining overall responsibility, the need to be aware of bias and the limitations of such tools. Importantly, this policy must highlight any confidentiality issues surrounding the sharing of manuscripts with AI tools. An example policy is provided in Appendix 1.

<u>Use of AI by peer reviewers</u>	<u>AI tools used by the review service</u>	<u>Auditing of AI tools</u>	<u>Monitoring & enforcement</u>	<u>Reporting</u>
Comprehensive list of acceptable and unacceptable use of AI tools by peer reviewers using the review platform. A list of accepted AI tools or LLMs is provided. Examples of AI use or guides/training are included.	Full disclosure of the tools used, including which AI tools are used, which versions, how they are used and how they are monitored for bias, hallucinations and equity.	Full disclosure on how the service audits the AI tools it uses which is updated yearly. The service shares the results of auditing.	Clear monitoring and enforcement guidance is provided, outlining how this is achieved and the consequences for content that breaches the AI policy. Public records of yearly reported cases and outcomes are provided for accountability and transparency.	There is a clear and dedicated reporting route, along with guidance on what can/should be reported. The process for handling reported content is publicly outlined.
Service lists examples of acceptable or unacceptable uses of AI by peer reviewers utilising their platforms.	Disclosure of AI tools used and how they are used.	Service relies on 3rd parties for audits of any AI tools used. Auditing may only occur at the point of first implementing the AI tool.	Service states that it actively monitors for AI content and discloses a clear pathway for enforcement of the AI policy.	Reporting of AI generated content follows the standard reporting process for complaints used by the review service.
Service does not allow any AI use by reviewers.	Service states that AI tools are used but does	Service does not audit any AI tools that it uses	Service does not monitor for AI use or enforce	Service does not provide a reporting route

	not provide a list of tools or state how they are used.		any AI policy.	
No guidance provided	No information provided	No auditing information provided	No clear monitoring or enforcement of policy	No information provided

N.b. Dark red = no or worst implementation, red = suggested/accepted actions, yellow = limited action, green = desired action.

Implement fields or forms to disclose AI use

Given the implausibility of completely preventing AI use during peer review, the best approach is to ensure responsible use. This can only be achieved if the use of AI is transparent as this enables readers and preprint review services to check the AI usage. To aid reviewers in being transparent in their use of AI in peer reviews, review services should include clear routes to disclosing this information. This could be guidance to include such AI use in the review or, preferably, in a specific entry field. Ideally, this should be included in metadata associated with the preprint review. Where guidance is provided, this would benefit from an example so that authors know exactly what information to include in such a disclosure.

As an alternative, or in combination with, a “use of AI” field, review platforms should consider creating a checkbox that reviewers are required to confirm as they upload their reviews. This would serve as a final reminder that humans should maintain final judgement and responsibility over review content. Additionally, this provides the review service with a route to remove AI-generated reviews that breach the policy.

If you used AI or large language model (LLM) tools in preparing this review, please describe how they were used (e.g., drafting text, editing, summarizing) and list the specific tools (e.g., ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini) and version. Your description should clearly indicate the extent and nature of AI assistance to ensure transparency. Please refer to the AI policy here.

Mock-up of a potential field to capture details of the use of AI in submitted peer review reports

I confirm that for any AI/LLM-generated content used in preparing this review, I have independently verified all information. I accept full responsibility for the accuracy, integrity, and appropriateness of the review in its entirety.

Mock-up of a confirmation checkbox for reviewer to confirm that they take responsibility for any use of AI in preparing their review

Training

Given the rapid expansion of AI tools, it is unsurprising that researchers are struggling to understand how to best use these tools and to do so responsibly. Appropriate training for reviewers is important in altering how they are using AI and to aid reviewers in complying with the review service policy. Such training should include clear overviews of the limitations and issues with AI tools, in addition to example-led mechanisms for responsible use. A key focus should conform to how the individual review services define “responsible” AI use. In addition to training for reviewers, review services need to provide training to staff/volunteers to ensure that they are equipped with an understanding of responsible AI use and appropriately auditing such tools.

Not all peer review services will be equipped or capable of providing necessary training to reviewers in the appropriate use of AI during peer review. However, where they cannot directly achieve this, review services should provide reviewers with independent materials and links to training. This training could be incorporated into pre-existing training programs, for example those that PREreview perform, or as a dedicated training session/program.

As a minimum, review services could consider providing basic guidance on using AI tools in peer review.

Auditing

As part of a commitment to continuous improvement and quality assurance, review services should implement a number of auditing processes related to AI. Whilst these may increase costs or time commitments, auditing of AI tools and the use of AI provides important insights and guidance. If the review service itself is utilising AI tools then auditing is essential to ensure that these tools are not impacting equity or introducing new sources of bias. Tools should be audited for their own policies around data that is entered into them, their governance structures and sustainability.

Even if the review service is not itself using AI tools, auditing of reviews being submitted is an important step in monitoring and tackling misuse by reviewers. For example, randomly sampling reviews to assess for quality and AI use would identify any issues or over-reliance on AI. Services may also want to consider implementing an automated process at the point of submitting reviews that screens for common AI phrases or responses. Any flagged reviews could then be checked by humans, although this could potentially be burdensome to review services with limited staff.

5 clear actionable steps to implement the best practices

1. Implement a transparent policy or code of practice focussed on or including AI
2. Provide guidance on responsible, appropriate and accepted AI use in reviewing
3. Create a field to capture AI use by reviewers to encourage transparency and full disclosure
4. Create a check box to encourage authors to confirm they take full responsibility for AI use
5. Audit AI tools and a random selection of reviews

These steps are provided as an infographic in Appendix 2 and downloadable [here](#).

About the author

Dr [Jonny Coates](#) holds a PhD in immune cell biology and is a recognised leading expert on preprints and academic culture. He has a strong track record in advocating for preprint adoption and improvements to the culture within academia. He created and hosts the [Preprints in Motion podcast](#) and has featured on numerous media outlets including BBC radio, Nature and The Economist. In 2024 he founded [Rippling Ideas](#), an organisation dedicated to advancing preprint adoption, fostering trust in research and improving the culture of academia. Contact jonny.coates@ripplingideas.org

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Appendix 1 - Example AI policy

At [Organisation], we recognize the evolving role of artificial intelligence (AI) and large language models (LLM) in science. This policy establishes clear guidelines for responsible AI use on our platform, balancing the benefits of AI tools with the need to uphold the integrity, originality, and accountability of all contributions.

1. Purpose and Rationale

[Organisation] is committed to fostering an environment of ethical and transparent scholarship. As AI technologies develop, we aim to provide clarity on their appropriate use to maintain the authenticity and reliability of all content shared on our platform.

2. Scope of Policy

This policy applies to all users of [Organisation], including:

- Community Members: Engaging in discussions, content creation, and knowledge sharing.
- [Organisation]: In creating resources and use of AI across the platform
- Peer Reviewers: Submitting preprint reviews on the [Organisation] platform.

3. Use of AI by peer reviewers

[Organisation] accepts the use of AI/LLM tools by peer reviewers on the condition that all usage is transparently declared and in accordance with this policy.

3A. Permitted tools

The following is a list of audited tools that [Organisation] approves in aiding the writing of peer reviews.

- Grammarly
- *[Ideally organisation to provide list of approved, audited tools]*

3B. Permitted Uses

- AI is permitted to improve readability and grammar, for example through the use of grammarly
- Humans must be fully accountable and responsible for any AI generated content

3C. Prohibited Uses

- AI must not be listed as authors or coauthors
- AI must not be used to substantially generate any of the peer review
- AI generated text should not be cited as a source
- Manuscripts should not be entered directly into AI tools, as this can be a breach of confidentiality

3D. Disclosure of AI use

- All AI use must be disclosed in the provided submission boxes
- Users must confirm that they have checked and take responsibility for any AI generated content

4. Use of AI by [Organisation]

[Organisation] uses various AI tools as outlined in this section. All tools are audited prior to use to ensure that any bias can be mitigated and that tools comply with [Organisations] privacy and data security policies

4A. Tools used by [Organisation] and how they are used

- [List out tools and their use; e.g. Tool X is used to identify potential peer reviewers]

5. Auditing of AI tools

Tools are audited for the following:

- Decision making process
- Bias
- Hallucinations and fabrications
- Accuracy of information
- Data privacy and security

6. Monitoring and enforcement

To ensure compliance with this policy, [Organisation] takes active steps to monitor peer reviews for content that potentially violates this policy.

- Automated and manual review: [Outline organisation processes]
- Peer reviews are monitored for standard language outputted by AI that would suggest a lack of human oversight
- Community reporting: Users of [Organisation] are encouraged to report potential violations of this policy
- Action: If reviews are found to breach this policy, [Organisation] will remove the reviews and, for repeated offences, individuals may be banned from the platform
- Transparent auditing: [Organisation] will provide a yearly report of AI content used in peer reviews and outcomes of breaches of this policy

7. Reporting violations

- For reviews that have been substantially written by AI or where AI has been used, individuals may report this to [Organisation - dedicated email or person/process]

8. Policy updates

This is a rapidly evolving area, and [Organisation] reserves the right to update this policy as necessary. The last update was: [DATE]

Appendix 2 - Infographic of 5 key actionable steps

5 ACTIONABLE STEPS TO IMPLEMENT AI BEST PRACTICES

For preprint review services

- 1 Implement an AI policy**

One of the most immediate steps a preprint review service can take is to implement a transparent, public, policy in relation to AI. This policy is useful even if the service does not allow AI use as this sets clear expectations to users
- 2 Provide guidance**

Appropriate training for reviewers is important in altering how they are using AI and to aid reviewers in complying with the review service policy. Such training should include clear overviews of the limitations and issues with AI tools, in addition to example-led mechanisms for responsible use
- 3 Capture AI use by reviewers**

To aid authors in being transparent in their use of AI in peer reviews, review services should include clear routes to disclosing this information
- 4 Encourage authors to take responsibility**

All final judgments on manuscript quality, originality, and scientific validity must be made by qualified human reviewers, not by AI alone
- 5 Audit AI tools**

As part of a commitment to continuous improvement and quality assurance, review services should implement a number of auditing processes related to AI. Even if the review service is not itself using AI tools, auditing of reviews being submitted is an important step in monitoring and tackling misuse by reviewers.

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